

Abstract

This paper investigates the condition of the Albuñuelas and Dúrcal rivers of the Restabal river region of southern Spain. The area is rural, mountainous, and largely agricultural, located close to Granada and the Sierra Nevadas, with extreme seasonality and semi-arid climate. By incorporating research via biological, chemical and physical water sampling, we were able to assess the biological health and water quality of the region. The results showed relatively healthy but polluted waters, and when combined with catchment knowledge, the likely source was attributed to agriculture, including over-fertilization, however further testing is required.

Introduction

It is important to understand anthropogenic effects on the biosphere, not only to react to negative human activities, but to prepare for them proactively as well. Due to rivers' catchment areas and the nature of bioaccumulation in pollutants, they are often one such place where anthropogenic activities, such as land-use, can be observed. Restabal of southern Spain, see figure 1, offers an opportunity to examine the biological, chemical and physical aspects of hydrology within the catchment, see figure 2. The aim is to assess the biological, chemical and physical data to determine quality and health of the Restabal river system, see figure 3. Objectives:

- Biological sampling to assess water health through macroinvertebrate diversity
- Chemical and physical water sampling to assess water quality
- Comparison of sites and overall assessment of river health

Figure 1: Map of Restabal in southern Spain. Source: Open Street Map

Figure 2: Sierra Nevada catchment (red), Albuñuelas (black). Source: Preston (2013)

Figure 3: Restabal sampling sites. Source: Open Street Map

Figures 4&5: Site 1

Figures 6&7: Site 2

Figure 8&9: Site 3

Figure 10: Site 4

Spain's unique climate greatly affects its river systems and how they function. This image, for example, see figure 11, shows the basic movements of water through a landscape.

However, the arid climate of southern Spain lacks much vegetation compared to the diagram. This decreases the total amount of water in the cycle, reducing the evapotranspiration, soil water storage, interception and biological storage abilities of the soil, thereby limiting the movement of sediment to wet seasons and extreme flooding events. During such times the precipitation will collect in

Figure 11: Isolated water catchment. Source: Holden (2018)

excess overland flow, saturated ground, and saturated bedrock, see figure 12.

In figure 12 the interception from vegetation may reduce pollutants able to enter the river and is another place in which Spain's climate supporting less vegetation greatly effects river

operations. It is important to understand the movement of water because the sediment it transports can contain contaminants or dangerous concentrations of naturally occurring substances from anywhere in the catchment. Any land-use in the catchment would be reflected in the water quality, such as high nitrogen or phosphorous levels due to agricultural use of fertilizer, which would cause eutrophication and subsequent low dissolved oxygen levels.

Figure 5: Hillslope run-off pathways. Source: Holden (2018)

Farming is an important part of life in the rural Restabal region, as it contributes to the nearly 60% of Spanish economic exports from agricultural crops (European Commission, 2021). The region is particularly known for its citrus and olives, with occasional guavas or avocados. The local farmers rely heavily on irrigation due to the high water demands of these crops (Gijón and Padial, n.d.). Fortunately, due to their proximity to the Sierra Nevadas and subsequent snow melt, rivers generally flow year-round. New farming tactics could greatly reduce the flow through new high density olive groves planted in Andalusia and southern Spain, as they are the primary producers of olives for the world (Guerrero-Casado *et al.*, 2021). Casado (2021) also explains the environmental consequences of such practices, specifically higher pressures on aquifers, springs, lakes, and other sources of freshwater. With more irrigation the potential for soil erosion and transportation will increase too. Knowing the effects of agricultural activities on soils, and how a catchment network operates, is important to understanding biological, chemical, and physical compositions of a river system to determine its health.

Materials and Methods

To collect the river data, we completed an impact surveying strategy, which is defined by the specificity of variables assessed and short amount of time and space used to do so (Chapman, 1996, p.26). Methods can be seen in table 1 below.

Sample type	Purpose	Equipment	Sampling Strategy	Limitations

Biological	Acquire macroinvertebrates to assess biological water quality	Net, beakers, buckets, water bib brace with boots, microscope, bins, tweezers, gloves, pipettes, slides, species categorisation booklets, taxa sheets	Disturbance, Simple random	Single sample, human error, river access, time of day, sun aspect
Turbidity	Acquire 12 samples over an hour to assess physical water quality	Beaker, water bib, turbidity light sensor test	Systematic - 1 sample every 5 minutes for an hour	One day of sampling, river access, vegetation cover, time of day, sun aspect
pH	Acquire 12 samples for chemical water quality	Beaker, water bib, pH meter	Systematic	Single sampling day, access, vegetation, time, sunlight
Conductivity	Acquire 12 samples for chemical water quality	Beaker, water bib, conductivity meter	Systematic	Single sampling day, access, vegetation, time, sunlight
Temperature	Acquire 12 samples for physical water quality	Beaker, water bib, thermometer	Systematic	Single sampling day, access, vegetation, time, sunlight
Dissolved Oxygen	Acquire 12 samples for chemical water quality	Beaker, water bib, dissolved oxygen meter	Systematic	Single sampling day, access, vegetation, time, sunlight
Velocity, depth and width	Measure basic river site for physical water quality	Water bib, tape measure, velocity meter	Simple random	Single sample, human error, river access, time of day, sun aspect

Table 1: Sampling strategies and methodologies completed January 26, 2024

Upon arrival at the site areas, each group began sampling in 5-minute intervals for the duration of an hour, at the beginning of which the biological samples were taken and placed in a shaded area with the lid placed on partially. Sites 1 and 2 were shallower in depth, at 18 and 19cm, which allowed for greater ease of sampling compared to site 3, with a depth of 31cm and width of 7.5m, along with site 4 at 50cm depth and 5.4m width, see site images 4-10 above. Velocity data, however, was slightly skewed due to the placement of the meter into the water, at all sites it was placed at the riverbed, but sites 1 and 2 were so shallow that the meter was barely under the surface. Sites 3 and 4 were much deeper and the velocity data was

seemingly low at less than 1m/s, which visually does not make sense, and is likely due to human error.

Data Analysis

The following day, the species were identified site by site with the help of identification booklet, slides, and occasional images from online. Taxa sheets used were the Biological Monitoring Working Party (BMWP) (Armitage *et al.*, 1983) which is specific to British rivers but used throughout Europe. Additionally, the IBMWP (Alba-Tercedor *et al.*, 2002), which is specific to Spain, and one ICM-11a (Munne and Prat, 2009), created specifically for Mediterranean rivers. Summary statistics were completed later and included mean, min, max, range, variance, standard variation, and standard error. Additionally, use of the AnalysisToolKit add-in on excel for statistical difference tests and descriptive statistics. A similar study, conducted in China's East Zhejiang Canal, also sampled macroinvertebrates in a similar way; counting and identifying the biota after collecting them from the river and calculating the BMWP through each species' general sensitivity to organic pollution (Jin *et al.*, 2024). The researchers additionally sampled similar physical and chemical properties of their water system as we did; however, they also tested many known human pollutants like nitrates, phosphates, and orthophosphates, probably due to the urban nature of their environment (Jin *et al.*, 2024). One team in Switzerland studying wastewater versus agricultural pollution effects on macroinvertebrates was able to return to a site previously visited in 2013 (Burdon *et al.*, 2019), something we were limited in, as the drought dried up the previously visited ephemeral rivers. Yet in Portugal, where the seasonal climate is comparable to Spain, Resende *et al.* (2009) explain that heavy metal from the industrial area was populating the north of the river catchment, whereas our catchment consists of largely rural and mountainous regions used for farming, making heavy metal testing largely irrelevant.

Results and Analysis

Biological

Graphic 1 presents the biological macroinvertebrate makeup of site 1 with the British, Spanish and Mediterranean indices. Under British river qualifications the site is a 5 on the 1-10 BMWP scale, putting it at moderate pollution levels. The Spain specific index puts the value a bit higher at 5.6, however the Mediterranean places it at 3.64, a much lower value in comparison to the others and a possible outlier. The most common species is Ephemerellidae; which exists in all Grades of water quality, unlike Tabanidae, which exists only in Grade II

(Xu *et al.*, 2013). The grading system as published by the Environmental Protection Administration in 2002 (as cited in Xu *et al.*, 2013), places Grades I and II at drinkable or good, III at moderate and seen in natural environments, IV is for industrial use and is poor quality, whereas V is only usable for agriculture and is described as very poor. Xu *et al.* (2013) also explains that Simuliidae, the second most common of site 1, favours Grades I-III and Erpobdellidae preferred Grades IV-V (Xu *et al.*, 2013). Besides the species in lowest abundance, the water quality seems as it would be on the higher side of moderate pollution that the indices describe.

Graphic 1: Site 1 macroinvertebrate taxa and indices

Graphic 2 displays the biological data from site 2 in a similar fashion with all 3 indices in top right corner and the respective species counts shown in the bar graph. Both the British and Spanish river indices place site 2 higher on the 1-10 scale, at 6.8 and 6.2, nearly 2 points and 1.5 points higher respectively, denoting it as slightly healthier than site 1. The Mediterranean index ranks site 2 slightly lower than the first, adding suspicion to this index's reliability for the locality. Chloroperlidae is most common in this site at 8 total and is known to have an intolerance to pollution (Xu *et al.*, 2013) with all 3 indices giving it a score of 10. Simuliidae are second most frequent at 6 counted individuals, and as noted above favour water quality Grades I-III, similarly, Baetidae is found in Grades I-IV (Xu *et al.*, 2013). Continuing in

descending order, Tipulidae is observed most frequently in Grade II waters while Ephemerelellidae, similarly to site 1, will exist in most of the range of water Grades (Xu *et al.*, 2013). A high-water grade is observed from the macroinvertebrates of site 2, though it is not unpolluted since no completely intolerant taxa are detected, and the indices additionally do not support that.

Graphic 2: Site 2 macroinvertebrate taxa and indices

Site 3 was by far the largest sum of macroinvertebrates at 11 different species, see graphic 3, resulting in a more diverse site than the other 3, and a Mediterranean index to represent that, as the number of families is a partial factor. It is possible that the factors which the ICM-11a index depend on, like the literal sense of how many families exist in the sample, are less proportional to Restabal specifically. Perhaps climate could play a role, as Spanish climate systems can differ to the rest of the Mediterranean. The British and Spanish indices are quite similar once again, within ~ 0.1 of each other at a moderate level of pollution once again. Simuliidae numbers were high at 22 counted individuals, have been found in each site so far and exist in water quality Grades I-III, similarly, Baetidae, at 11 total, have been in site 2, now site 3 and are found in Grades I-IV along with Gammaridae of which 7 were counted (Xu *et al.*, 2013). Alternatively, Tipulidae, seen as well in site 2, is often only found in Grade

II waters, unlike Oligochaeta, which exist in most waters and will occasionally signify a polluted environment through their habitation (Xu *et al.*, 2013). Glossiphoniidae, Hydropsychidae, and Planariidae are commonly found in polluted areas suffering specifically from rural wastewater and agricultural practices like overfertilization inciting run-off into waterways (Cao, Bark and Williams, 1996). Lastly, Xu *et al.* (2013) state Libellulidae is considered a “pollution-tolerant taxa” (‘Materials and Methods’, para.7) meanwhile Leptophlebiidae is less tolerant, seen only in water quality Grades I and II. The invertebrates which had a high pollution tolerance were in less abundance compared to those which were in water quality Grades I-III, signifying a likely agricultural source of pollution.

Graphic 3: Site 3 macroinvertebrate taxa and indices

Graphic 4 shows site 4 biological data, including indices of an exactly similar BMWP and IBMWP at 5.6, the second highest value after site 2. The Spanish index is quite low in comparison to the other sites, possibly due to the lack of indicator and pollution intolerant organisms. Leptophlebiidae has the largest occurrence at 11 individuals, this species is a decent indicator species as it exists in only water Grades I and II, Baetidae however, are found in Grades I-IV making it a pollution tolerant taxon (Xu *et al.*, 2013). Xu *et al.* (2013) continues that Simuliidae, along with Chironomidae are observed in Grades I-III, with the later seen in IV and V as well making them both extremely pollution tolerant as well. All but

Chironomidae have been in at least 2 of the other sites, likely due to this site sample's location geographically downstream of both rivers.

Graphic 4: Site 4 macroinvertebrate taxa and indices

Chemical

The turbidity data was put through basic statistics to determine the mean and confidence level to 95% which were used to create a graph of the means by site, see graphic 5. Though there is a visible difference between sites 1 and 2 and 3 and 4, a t-test was preformed which did determine this as true along with another visual of the data over the time it was collected, see graphic 6. Accepted turbidity values for drinking water are less than 1NTU (WHO, 2011), which the site data visibly does not meet and can be attributed to the agricultural use of the river.

Graphic 5: Turbidity means by site

Graphic 6: Turbidity comparison by site and t-test

The conductivity data was similarly statistically analysed, see graphic 7, visual difference determined, and t-test completed, see graphic 8, which showed a significant difference.

Conductivity or total dissolved solids have guideline levels of less than 900µs/cm (WHO, 2011), which all data values fall within.

Graphic 7: Conductivity means by site

Graphic 8: Conductivity comparison by site and t-test

Graphic 9 shows dissolved oxygen means, and despite an overall difference between sites 1 and 2, the Albuñuelas, and sites 3 and 4, the Dúrcal, the error bars display the lack of significance. WHO (2011) states no health-based guidelines for dissolved oxygen, other than the ideal of low nitrogen and phosphorus to reduce possible eutrophication in high dissolved oxygen environments.

Graphic 9: Dissolved oxygen means by site

The pH means, see graphic 10, show again the lack of certain difference between the sites, as the confidence levels and mean values are not distinctly different enough. Threshold values for pH are 6.5-8.5 (WHO, 2011), with solely site 1 mean exceeding that value.

Graphic 10: pH means by site

The mean temperature by site, see graphic 11, is possibly statistically significant, however as the data was not taken at the same time of day, it is quite possible that the sun began to heat up the water during the later part of the day. Generally accepted temperature guidelines are those below 25C (WHO, 2011), all data falls within that range.

Graphic 11: Temperature means by site

Discussion

Biological

The macroinvertebrate data was proof of life in all 4 sites, some with more than others, though those invertebrates observed were more often generalists able to adapt quickly in poor environmental conditions. In site 1 4:6 species were generalists, surviving in 3 water quality Grades or more. Site 2 had a ratio of 3:5, site 3; 8:10, and site 4 4:5, which leads to all sites having >50% generalists, with sites 3 and 4 containing especially pollution tolerant taxa at 80%. One study specifically states that extreme nutrient enrichment leads to reduced specialist species and their niche environments (Dong *et al.*, 2024), thereby selecting generalist species, who, because of their niche flexibility, making them poor indicators of water quality, can adapt quickly to environmental changes. The high percentage of these generalist species in all 4 sites displays the potential of a harmful eutrophication of the waterways. Though this could be from anywhere in the catchment, it is likely from the agricultural practices such as overuse of fertilizers and pesticides. The excess would be

transported by rain easily over the steep slopes to meet the major river valley and begin to contaminate the system. The human selection of generalist species leads to more generalist species through reproduction. Due to this, specialists are often forced to use off season reproductive times to avoid competing with generalists which are more likely to succeed (Dong *et al.*, 2024). Dong *et al.* (2024) suggests that even after, “decreased degrees of eutrophication after restoration, high levels of nutrients remained at these sites that could only support highly tolerant species” (Sec.4.3, para.3). The increase of generalists decreases biodiversity, demonstrating the importance of specialists like indicator species to determine the health of water systems.

Physical

Physical data from the sites were velocity, possibly skewed, depth, and information like basic soil descriptions can be ascertained as well. The velocity in sites 1 and 2 were on average higher than sites 3 and 4, though depth was on average lower in sites 3 and 4 than 1 and 2. Sites 1 and 2 had a finer grain bed of silty sand rendering the sediment more able to become trapped in the water, rather than the rocky bottom of sites 3 and 4, plus smaller flows like this one tend to contain the contents of their own soil bed (Holloway and Dahlgren, 2001). Additionally, the river velocity was higher, so there is greater energy to move the sediments into the water column and yield high turbidity.

Chemical

However, in addition to this, higher turbidity also carries eroded material from the entire catchment, making it hard to trace. The Dúrcal sites evidently contained more dissolved material than the Albuñuelas, as those values were significantly higher. This could be due to the Dúrcal’s larger and more elevated catchment area and is possibly due to the wet season flushing any loose sediments from the soil and into the nearest watershed (Holloway and Dahlgren, 2001). Dissolved oxygen levels, though not statistically significant, show that site 2, a shallow and very vegetated water environment, held the highest relative values. This was likely the preferred habitat of all 4 sites for organic life. The pH across all sites was comparatively basic at ~8-8.5, which would diminish the invertebrate life, however the larvae have less sensitivities to more basic pHs during their growing cycles (Hou *et al.*, 2020). Temperature was not tested for significance due to the heat change during the day, though the riparian buffer of the Dúrcal, in addition to the depth would usually mean a cooler temperature, though this was not seen, possibly attributed to its larger catchment area.

Conclusion

In summary, the water quality and biological health of the Albuñuelas and Dúrcal of the Restabal region of southern Spain indicate a slightly polluted, generalist species abundant environment. To be certain of the cause of the pollution, testing for nitrogen, phosphorous and potassium would be essential as they are common fertilizers, along with more testing dates throughout the year to avoid extreme seasonality in the data. In addition to this, soil sampling throughout the local area would help to apply slope and soil aspects to the transport processes near the river, making surveying of the local land-use in-person would be a good addition. Land-use changes can be observed in these places where human activity affects the nature of catchment areas through overfertilization through such processes as bioaccumulation. Research like this must be done to interpret humans' effects on the biosphere to react to and prepare for negative anthropogenic outcomes.

Reference List

- Alba-Tercedor, J., Jáimez-Cuéllar, P., Álvarez, M., Avilés, J. and Bonada, N. (2002). *Caracterización Del Estado Ecológico De Ríos Mediterráneos Ibéricos Mediante El Índice IBMWP (antes BMWP')*. [online] Available at: <https://diposit.ub.edu/dspace/bitstream/2445/32903/1/523712.pdf> [Accessed 13 Mar. 2024].
- Armitage, P., Moss, D., Wright, J. and Furse, M. (1983). The Performance of a New Biological Water Quality Score System Based on Macroinvertebrates over a Wide Range of Unpolluted running-water Sites. *Water Research*, [online] 17(3), pp.333–347. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/0043-1354\(83\)90188-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0043-1354(83)90188-4).
- Burdon, F.J., Munz, N.A., Reyes, M., Focks, A., Joss, A., Räsänen, K., Altermatt, F., Eggen, R.I.L. and Stamm, C. (2019). Agriculture versus Wastewater Pollution as Drivers of Macroinvertebrate Community Structure in Streams. *Science of The Total Environment*, [online] 659, pp.1256–1265. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.12.372>.
- Cao, Y., Bark, A.W. and Williams, W.P. (1996). Measuring the Responses of Macroinvertebrate Communities to Water pollution: a Comparison of Multivariate approaches, Biotic and Diversity Indices. *Hydrobiologia*, [online] 341(1), pp.1–19. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/bf00012298>.

- Chapman, D.V., Unesco, World Health Organization and United Nations Environment Programme (2007). *Water Quality Assessments : a Guide to the Use of biota, sediments, and Water in Environmental Monitoring*. [online] London ; New York: E & Fn Spon. Available at:
<https://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/rhul/detail.action?docID=6128138> [Accessed 13 Mar. 2024].
- Dong, R., Peng, K., Zhang, Q., Heino, J., Cai, Y. and Gong, Z. (2024). Spatial and Temporal Variation in Lake Macroinvertebrate Communities Is Decreased by Eutrophication. *Environmental Research*, [online] 243, p.117872.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.117872>.
- European Commission (2021). *Agriculture and Rural Development Statistical Factsheet*. [online] Available at: https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-12/agri-statistical-factsheet-es_en_0.pdf [Accessed 13 Mar. 2024].
- Guerrero-Casado, J., Carpio, A.J., Tortosa, F.S. and Villanueva, A.J. (2021). Environmental Challenges of Intensive Woody crops: the Case of Super high-density Olive Groves. *Science of the Total Environment*, [online] 798, p.149212.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.149212>.
- Holden, J. (2017). *An Introduction to Physical Geography and the Environment*. 4th ed. [online] Harlow, England: Pearson Education Limited. Available at:
<https://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/rhul/detail.action?docID=5175093&query=holden> [Accessed 13 Mar. 2024].
- Holloway, J. and Dahlgren, R. (2001). Seasonal and event-scale Variations in Solute Chemistry for Four Sierra Nevada Catchments. *Journal of Hydrology*, [online] 250(1-4). Available at:
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022169401004243> [Accessed 13 Mar. 2024].
- Hou, Y., Kong, F., Li, Y., Xi, M. and Yu, Z. (2020). Key Factors of the Studies on Benthic Macroinvertebrate in Coastal wetlands: Methods and Biodiversity. *Ecohydrology & Hydrobiology*, [online] 20(3), pp.424–436.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecohyd.2020.02.004>.
- Jin, X., Lan, X., Sun, H., Hu, B. and Wang, B. (2023). Assessment of Water Quality Using Benthic Diatom and Macroinvertebrate assemblages: a Case Study in an East China

- Canal. *Water Biology and Security*, [online] 3(1), p.100231.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watbs.2023.100231>.
- Munné, A. and Prat, N. (2009). Use of macroinvertebrate-based Multimetric Indices for Water Quality Evaluation in Spanish Mediterranean rivers: an Intercalibration Approach with the IBMWP Index. *Hydrobiologia*, [online] 628(1), pp.203–225.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-009-9757-1>.
- Resende, P.C., Resende, P., Pardal, M., Almeida, S. and Azeiteiro, U. (2009). Use of Biological Indicators to Assess Water Quality of the UI River (Portugal). *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, [online] 170(1-4), pp.535–544.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-009-1255-4>.
- Rodríguez Gutiérrez, F. (n.d.). *Notes for a History of Farming in the Lecrin Valley*. [online] www.adurcal.com. Available at: <https://www.adurcal.com/enlaces/ingles/5.htm> [Accessed 13 Mar. 2024].
- Secretario de Estado de Medio Ambiente (2013). *Protocolo De Calculo Del Índice IBMWP*. [online] Available at: https://www.miteco.gob.es/content/dam/mitesco/es/agua/temas/estado-y-calidad-de-las-aguas/IBMWP-2013_24_05_2013_tcm30-175292.pdf [Accessed 13 Mar. 2024].
- World Health Organisation (2011). *Guidelines for Drinking-water Quality Fourth Edition*. [online] Available at: https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/44584/9789241548151_eng.pdf [Accessed 13 Mar. 2024].
- Xu, M., Wang, Z., Duan, X. and Pan, B. (2013). Effects of Pollution on Macroinvertebrates and Water Quality bio-assessment. *Hydrobiologia*, [online] 729(1), pp.247–259.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-013-1504-y>.

Appendices

Biological

species	site 1	site 2	site 3	site 4
Leptophlebiidae			4	11
Libellulidae			4	
Rhyachomyiidae	1		3	3
Gammaridae			7	
Hydropsychidae			4	
Tipulidae		3	9	
Simuliidae	2	6	22	4
Planariidae			2	
Baetidae		4	11	5
Glossiphoniidae			2	
Oligochaeta			6	
Erpobdellidae	1			
Veliidae	1			
Tabanidae	1			
Ephemerellidae	5	2		
Chloroperlidae		8		
Chironomidae				2

Appendix 1: Biological taxa counts

Chemical and Physical

time	turbidity (NTU)	pH (0-14)	conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	temperature (C)	dissolved oxygen ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{L}$)
12:50	317.1	8.491	532	13	9.65
12:55	341.5	8.496	532	12.7	10.05
13:00	321.2	8.533	534	12.7	9.7
13:05	297.6	8.528	531	12.9	9.7
13:10	279.4	8.524	533	13	10.4
13:15	361.3	8.543	526	14	9.92
13:20	474.7	8.564	533	12.9	9.92
13:25	391.3	8.592	530	13.8	9.72
13:30	272.6	8.585	532	13.2	9.62
13:35	410.2	8.512	538	13.4	9.4
13:40	242.1	8.5	530	13.9	9.46
13:45	248.2	8.536	532	13.3	9.62

Appendix 2: Site 1 water chemistry

velocity avg (m/s)	velocity std dev (m/s)		
1.205	0.016		
1.2 m width			
Depth 1 (cm)	Depth 2		Depth 3
16	18		13

Appendix 3: Site 1 physical water qualities

time	turbidity (NTU)	pH (0-14)	conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	temperature (C)	dissolved oxygen ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{L}$)
11:10	324.3	8.352	536	11.6	10.15
11:25	324.8	8.401	532	12.3	9.85
11:30	321.9	8.375	542	12.2	10
11:35	315.2	8.391	534	12.1	9.93
11:40	321.2	8.421	538	12.3	10.02
11:45	370.3	8.38	543	12.5	10.9
11:50	349.2	8.385	540	12.4	9.62
11:55	329.2	8.467	535	12.4	9.81
12:00	303.5	8.4	600	12.4	10.23
12:05	334.2	8.444	545	12.3	9.76
12:10	317.8	8.42	539	12.3	9.97
12:15	323.7	8.427	551	12.3	9.91

Appendix 4: Site 2 water chemistry

velocity avg (m/s)	velocity std dev (m/s)		
0.82	0.023		
2.2 width (m)			
Depth 1 (cm)	Depth 2		Depth 3
17	19		11

Appendix 5: Site 2 physical water qualities

Time	Turbidity (NTU)	pH (0-14)	Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	Temperature (C)	Dissolved Oxygen ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{L}$)
11:45	8.57	8.35	595	14.8	9.67
11:50	9.19	8.45	597	14.9	9.49
11:55	12.7	8.42	599	14.7	9.63
12:00	9.3	8.4	601	14.5	9.97
12:05	15.47	8.46	604	14.4	9.68
12:10	9.87	8.32	604	14.4	9.75
12:15	9.74	8.55	605	14.6	9.7
12:20	143.2	8.53	601	15.4	9.65
12:25	11.42	8.49	599	15	9.69
12:30	13.6	8.51	600	15.4	9.62
12:35	11.31	8.45	600	15.2	9.64
12:40	12.11	8.42	598	15.3	9.55

Appendix 6: Site 3 water chemistry

velocity avg (m/s)	velocity std dev (m/s)	
0.3	0.152	Depth 1
0.066	0.12	Depth 2
0.162	0.045	Depth 3
7.5 width (m)		
Depth 1 (cm)	Depth 2	Depth 3
31	31	31

Appendix 7: Site 3 physical water qualities

Time	Turbidity (NTU)	pH (0-14)	Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	Temperature (C)	Dissolved Oxygen ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{L}$)
14:00	12.74	8	586	17.4	9.07
14:05	12.29	8.38	584	17.3	9.19
14:10	16.77	8.18	586	16.5	8.95
14:15	19.17	8.19	590	16.5	9.93
14:20	28.64	8.26	585	17	9.73
14:25	17.29	8.18	599	16	9.43
14:30	35.09	8.26	600	15.9	9.53
14:35	145.1	8.24	595	16	9.78
14:40	17.07	8.247	596	16.4	9.11
14:45	15.54	8.62	601	16.1	9.07
14:50	15.35	8.46	608	16.2	9.44
14:55	17.48	8.5	610	15.9	9.55

Appendix 8: Site 4 water chemistry

Velocity avg (m/s)	Velocity std dev (m/s)	
0.0454	0.04	Depth 1
0.0789	0.06	Depth 2
0.841	0.084	Depth 3
width	depth	
1.8	15	Depth 1
3.6	42	Depth 2
5.4	50	Depth 3

Appendix 9: Site 4 physical water qualities